

The Data Strand

3 October 2022

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AGU's position statement on data affirms that

“Earth and space science data are a world heritage, and an essential part of the science ecosystem. All players in the science ecosystem—researchers, repositories, publishers, funders, institutions, etc.—should work to ensure that relevant scientific evidence is processed, shared, and used ethically, and is available, preserved, documented, and fairly credited.”

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150 years of *Nature*

A century and a half of research and discovery.

INTERNATIONAL COLLABORATIONS

Author lists on research publications show a shift towards multinational teams; fewer teams are composed entirely of researchers from one country.

Proportion of papers

■ Multinational ■ Domestic ■ Single author

Monastersky, R., & Van Noorden, R. (2019). 150 years of Nature: a data graphic charts our evolution. *Nature*, 575(7781), 22–23.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-019-03305-w>

The Future of your Research

- Research Teams (not individuals)
- International Collaborations
- Robust **tools to discover** relevant research worldwide
- Good **documentation** to understand that research, data, and/or software
- Data that is **interoperable**, no matter which research team created it
- Software that is **accessible** and developed in current tools (e.g., Jupyter Notebooks)
- Licenses that support **reuse**.

FAIR Guiding Principles

FAIR is...

Findable

Accessible

Interoperable

Reusable

Article in Nature journal *Scientific Data*:
Wilkinson, M. D. *et al.* The FAIR Guiding Principles
for scientific data management and stewardship.
Sci. Data 3:160018 doi: 10.1038/sdata.2016.18
(2016).

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Source: <https://www.andis.org.au/working-with-data/fairdata/training>

Is FAIR Open? In short, “It depends.”

Data can be FAIR or Open, both or neither.

The greatest potential for reuse comes when data are both FAIR and Open.

Higman, Rosie, Daniel Bangert, and Sarah Jones. 2019. “Three Camps, One Destination: The Intersections of Research Data Management, FAIR and Open”. *Insights* 32 (1): 18. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.1629/uksg.468>

Data should be as open as possible, as closed as necessary.

Why do we Care about FAIR?

RESEARCHERS ♥ DATA MANAGEMENT!

HMM... WHAT DATA IS OUT THERE ...

Wow! SUPER RELEVANT USEFUL DATA!

Now... TO SUBMIT MY unique & valuable RESEARCH DATA.

Why DOES THE DATA MANAGER INSIST ON SO MUCH METADATA?

DATA MANAGERS ... MAKING DATA MORE USEFUL ... AND PAVING THE WAY FOR FUTURE RESEARCHERS TO FIND VALUE IN YOUR DATA!

Shelley

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HMM... WHAT DATA IS OUT THERE ...

... TO SUPPORT MY RESEARCH?

ULTRA SPECIFIC
METADATA
SEARCH CRITERIA

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Open Science – Transparency and Trust

“Increased openness leads to increased transparency and trust in scientific information...”

Source: UNESCO
Recommendation on Open
Science; adopted
November 2021

<https://en.unesco.org/science-sustainable-future/open-science>

Open Science – The Key Pillars

- Open scientific knowledge
 - **Scientific publications**
 - **Open research data**
 - **Open source software and source code**
 - **Open hardware**
- Open science infrastructures
- Science communication
- Open engagement of societal actors
- Open dialogue with other knowledge systems.

Source: UNESCO
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From the very beginning of the research process,

the researcher **both contributes** to open science and

takes advantage of the open science practices of other members of the research community.

Wai...wai...wait.

This is all new to me!

What do you mean
this matters to my
research?!?

Building Your Open Science Skills

- **You, the Researcher:** How you and your work are discovered, made visible, and get recognition
- **Your Research Team/Lab:** Working Openly
- **Your Community:** Improving interoperability, sharing, and reuse beyond your team
- **Beyond Your Community:** Preparing for Cross-domain challenges

**You, the Researcher:
How you and your work are
discovered, made visible, and get
recognition**

- **Digital Presence**
- **Data Documentation and Citation**
- **Software Documentation and Citation**

A top-down view of a spiral of smooth, multi-colored stones (white, yellow, orange, black, grey, blue) arranged on a sandy surface. The stones form a clockwise spiral starting from the center and moving outwards. A white line points from the text box on the right towards the center of the spiral.

Your Research Team/Lab: Working Openly

- **Research/Project Team
Open Science Practices**
- **Resources and
Lab/Team Guidelines**
- **Research/Project Team
Digital Objects
Preservation Checklist**

**Your Community:
Improving interoperability,
sharing, and reuse beyond your
team**

- **Transparency and Understanding**
- **Usability**
- **Trust and Persistence**

Beyond Your Community: Preparing for Cross-domain challenges

- **Computational Notebooks**
- **Executable Environments**
- **Working with International Teams**

Let's Start the Journey to Open Science...

- Digital Presence
- Data Documentation and Citation
- Software Documentation and Citation

PARSEC Community on Zenodo.com

- Digital Presence Checklist.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4706118>
- Data Documentation and Citation Checklist.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7062402>
- Software Documentation and Citation Checklist.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7062413>

What is your Digital Presence?

1. How **you and your research** appear in online content.
2. How well **your work is integrated and connected** in the scientific record through your publications, datasets, software, and other digital objects and content.

You are previewing the public version of your record **0000-0003-2926-8353** [Edit this record](#)

Printable version

[https://orcid.org/
0000-0003-2926-8353](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2926-8353)

Name

Shelley Stall

Biography

Shelley Stall is the Vice President for the American Geophysical Union's Data Leadership Program. She works with AGU's members, their organizations, and the broader research community to improve data and digital object practices with the ultimate goal of elevating how research data is managed and valued. Better data management results in better science. Shelley's diverse experience working as a program and project manager, software architect, database architect, performance and optimization analyst, data product provider, and data integration architect for international communities, both nonprofit and commercial, provides her with a core capability to guide development of practical and sustainable data policies and practices ready for adoption and adapting by the broad research community.

Activities

[Collapse all](#)

Employment (1)

Sort

American Geophysical Union: Washington, DC, US

2015-06-22 to present | Vice President (Data Leadership)
Employment

[Show more detail](#)

Source: Shelley Stall

Emails

sshall@agu.org

Websites & social links

[AGU Blog and Resources - Data Leadership](#)

[AGU Data Leadership Program](#)

Keywords

Open Science, FAIR Data and Software, Data Citation, Software Citation

Quarterly

Founded: 2018

E-ISSN: 2641-435X

More About *Data Intelligence*

Journal Resources

Editorial Info

Abstracting and Indexing

Growing the FAIR Community at the Intersection of the Geosciences and Pure and Applied Chemistry

[Shelley Stall](#) , [Lesley Wyborn](#),
[Nancy Hoebelheinrich](#) and [Ian Bruno](#)

Posted Online November 01, 2019

https://doi.org/10.1162/dint_a_00036

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ORCID

Crossref DOI

Soon to be released...

Your Research Team/Lab: Working Openly (Spiral Two)

- Research/Project Team Open Science Practices
- Resources and Lab/Team Guidelines
- Research/Project Team Digital Objects Preservation Checklist

Additional Languages and Supporting Videos

- Portuguese
- Spanish
- French
- Japanese

AGU Data & Software Sharing Guidance

What is covered:

- What data needs to be available?
- Repository Selection
- Availability Statement
- Data & Software Citation
- Citation Formatter
- Models & Simulations
- Journal Specific Guidance
- International Geo Sample Numbers
- Data Help Desk

JOIN RENEW GIVE LOGIN Q ☰

Data & Software for Authors

WHAT IS NEEDED?

AGU requires that the underlying data needed to understand, evaluate, and build upon the reported research be available at the time of peer review and publication. Additionally, authors should make available software that has a significant impact on the research. This entails:

1. Depositing the data and software in a trusted repository, as appropriate, and preferably with a DOI
2. Including an [Availability Statement](#) as a separate paragraph in the Open Research section explaining to the reader where and how to access the data and software
3. And including [citation\(s\)](#) to the deposited data and software, in the Reference Section

Click on the headings below for detailed information on:

- [Models & Simulations](#)
- [Journal-Specific Data Guidance](#)
- [International Geo Sample Numbers](#)

Most of your questions regarding data and software should be answered by the resources below. Just in case, if you still have questions, you can contact DataHelp@agu.org

WHAT DATA NEEDS TO BE AVAILABLE?

Primary and processed data used for your research should be preserved and made available. Generally, the underlying data are considered to be the types of data usually preserved in domain repositories for each discipline. These may include raw data, but are usually the processed or refined data that support and lead to the described results and allow other readers to assess your conclusions and build off your work.

In your paper, cite these data, as well as any data you used from other sources, and include information about access to the data in the availability statement. For [model or simulation data](#), follow [journal specific guidance](#) on prioritizing preserved output; in general, availability of software is most important.

Very large data (greater than 1 terabyte or TB) can be a challenge to preserve as there often fees and additional resources required. One option to consider, institutions often offer solutions for data preservation and compliance. Again, refer to the [journal specific guidance](#) for more information or email DataHelp@agu.org.

<https://www.agu.org/Publish-with-AGU/Publish/Author-Resources/Data-and-Software-for-Authors>

Manage your Digital Objects –
Research Team Member Checklist

Digital Presence - Connect your
research for better discovery

Guidance for AGU Authors - Jupyter
Notebooks

Software Citation - 5 Tips

CoreTrustSeal Cohort - AGU
Enabling FAIR Data Project

AGU ADVANCING EARTH AND SPACE SCIENCE
Data and Software Sharing
Guidance for Authors Submitting to
AGU Journals

Data and Software Availability and
Citation Checklist

Domain-Discipline Repositories
Useful to AGU Journals

AGU's Paleocyanography and
Paleoclimatology - Data Submission
Quick Guide

Guidance for AGU Authors - R Scripts
and Markdown

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Thank you

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This work is generously funded through grants from:

